

DYNAMICS OF CAREER ASPIRATION OF TRIBAL UNDERGRADUATES

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1. Introduction

“To find out what one is fitted to do, and to secure an opportunity to do that, is the key to happiness” - John Dewey

‘Man’s most ancient preoccupation – work, has today yielded the inspiration of career and it is the most important aspect of the overall development of the human individual. From flint to microchip the idea of career gets various different transformations over the ages’ (Arulmani 2009). Further, the impact of globalization has quickened the pace for expansion and transformation all over the world and this has thrown up multiple career options for living. Career is ‘a field for or pursuit of consecutive progressive achievement especially in public, professional, or business life’ as defined in Merriam Webster Dictionary (2015). Career aspiration is epistemologically dealt with individual’s actual objective to be what he or she wants in life, pertaining to what type of vocation or profession they want to pursue. Aspiration is defined as “A students’ ability to identify and set goals for the future, while being inspired in the present to work toward those goals” (Quaglia & Cobb, 1996). In social-personal dimension it is a mechanism whereby society utilizes the services of its members to contribute to its wellbeing, progress and development. It is not only means of individual’s livelihood but also the identity of self. Since, Indian society is highly complex and hierarchical, it results various connotations of career and career related trajectories for the individuals. ‘In India as caste system is the resultant of Varna systems which has began to fade, class and prestige-based approach to career gets subtle but strong influence on work behaviour’ (Arulmani 2009); then career finds its being at the confluence of the two great streams of influences on individual development—his biology and his socialization. Career is an individual’s life goal; although a work done under any career is neutral in nature whereas aspiration can be of manifested and expressed.

With globalization, advanced technology and high tech communication, numerous opportunities divulge and its implication is felt everywhere in industries and education as well. And so the students who are the ultimate stakeholders whose career aspiration is a significant factor for not only to personal success but also to simultaneous augmentation of any futuristic development of society at large. Aspirations are what drive individuals to do more and be more than they presently are. 'We may know what we are, but we cannot know for certain what we can be' (Robert A. et al, 1989). It is a craving for high achievement in life. It is a crucial aspect of individual's motivation, since it determines individual efforts towards attaining career goals. Dynamism seen in development of career aspiration is due to a number of factors. The significant factors that influence are culture, family environment and socio-economic status, locality of residence, teaching commitment and educational aspiration and others.

Statement of the problem

In today's educational world, students are pressed with numerous demands from either of parents, peers, neighbours and current situations which emphasize them to do well in academics or technical education whatever they are pursuing. In such a milieu adolescent students, especially tribal adolescents in the Indian continent feel discomfited and it has been evidenced highest school dropout, early marriage and other social issues debarring them from having both educational and higher career aspiration. As students in general, strive towards their aspirations and so in socio-economic perspective, the transition from the traditional practices towards imbibing new learning in globalised surroundings, tribal communities' aspiration similarly may get reflected with its students' career aspiration. Even in these times of fast media and instant news, huge numbers of students are not having a specific career goal in their mind. The focal point is that as notion of career becoming widespread, so is the necessity of having a developed system that will optimize students' engagement in career development possibly by developing higher level of aspiration, and that indirectly contributes for development of society i.e. tribal society.

2. Review of literature

Plentiful literature is available in the subject line 'career aspiration' but relevant to exclusive literature in tribal students' career aspiration in Indian context is very meager. So the researcher, to recap the importance of career aspiration of students and its rear side dynamics, considers a few works which indirectly and directly postulate on.

Frank Person (1920s) who's been called as father of Career Psychology, talks about personality traits related with matching a specific career i.e. occupation. Individuals are

unique and their personal qualities---like, dislike, attitude towards dignity of work and so on influence to prefer certain groups of works or jobs.

Donald Super (1950s) suggested that career development is process that spans across individual's life. There are certain specific stages: i) Growth, ii) Exploration, iii) Establishment, iv) Maintenance and v) Decline; therefore individual undergoes these stages one by one and during exploration as well as in initial establishment stages his /her career aspiration comprehensively related with his/her self concept.

Bandura (1970s) unlike Frank Person, Donald Super and Holland, he calls attention to the situational and sociological factors for development career choice. His Self –Efficacy theory as well as Social Learning theory propose that individual's self efficacy and societal and environmental influences absorb vitally for any career decision making or career choice. For Bandura 'People are more likely to act based on their beliefs', 'People learn by watching what others do and the human thought process influences the careers we choose'. These beliefs regularly change base on interactions with other people, environment, and one's own behavior.

Holland (1980s) stresses on psychological factors that are responsible for career decision making. His proposition is in the line 'personality type matching working environment'; so the common themes of his theory go like: i) 'Occupation choice is an expression of personality and not random', ii) 'Members of an occupational group have similar personalities', iii) 'People in each group will respond to situations an problems similarly' and iv) 'Occupational achievement, stability and satisfaction depends on congruence between one's personality and job environment'.

Grewal (1973), Akhilesh (1991), Desai and Whiteside (2000), they in their studies found that dominated belief and environmental factors are responsible for career choice behaviour of Indian students

Arulmani (2009) found, there is significant relation between higher level career aspiration and socio-economic condition of the students; his study findings indicate higher the socio-economic status representing higher level of career aspiration and the versa-vice. Some of psychological factors namely self efficacy, achievement motivation and academic performance etc play a crucial role i.e. dynamics for development higher level of career aspiration.

Therefore, out of limitedness of studies directly related with career aspiration of tribal students and that too of tribal undergraduates , this study is sort of exploration on the career issues with special context of 'tribal students' in Odisha in India.

3.Method

This descriptive exploratory study aims to analyze how 120 tribal students who are in their final year of under graduation (UG) in different general academic disciplines .i.e. Arts, Science and Commerce. The simple direct approach has been taken to collect the data randomly. Respondents were selected after scrutinizing the strength (numbers) in their respective discipline specific attendance registers; lottery method was taken for simple random sample. Besides, in informal situations the target groups were interviewed to have a few case studies. So case studies along with simple percentage analysis was undertaken to explore different dynamics behind their career aspiration. This study is different from the sampling logic, as because qualitative as well as quantitative data were collected for research purpose. One may say it is a sort of mixed method.

Research participants

40 students each from three different disciplines i.e. Arts, Science & Commerce were interviewed to seek information about their i) Perception about Career ii) Name of Career/Profession they want to be in, iii) After 5 years where you will be, iv) Being in your chosen career what will be your most important achievement/s and v) What will you do if not preferred career happens? From each discipline with help of convenience sampling proportionate number of boys and girls were undertaken in this study. The participants in this study were from a self-financing autonomous college where in an enabling environment all sorts of modern educational facilities e.g. internet, state of art library, coaching and placements, exposures, mentoring and guidance and career counseling provided to them.

Research instrument

Five semi-structured open ended interview questions were designed to investigate how the students perceived about their career. In addition, Career Aspiration Scale (Modern version 2015, M.A George & O' Brien) was used to measure level of career aspiration. The tool was created by experts, and is often used by social scientists and career psychologists. Career Aspiration Scale which developed by O'Brien (1992), the Career Aspiration Scale (CAS) is a 24-items, 5-point, Likert-type scale that ranges from (0) 'not at all true of me' to (4) 'very true of me'. The scale is designed to measure participants' goals and plans within their chosen careers. Only items related to Achievement Aspiration and Educational Aspiration are (16 items) adopted and used as instrument for this study. So the adopted scale's scores on the CAS range from 0 to 64 and higher scores representing higher career aspiration. It was transcribed into local language to have better response from the student respondents.

Data collection and data analysis

Data were collected from Kalinga Institute of Social Sciences (KISS), the world largest tribal residential educational institution. The residential educational institute is working on holistic development of the tribals by providing all amenities free along with quality education. The concept of 'home away from home' finds true expression in this campus with 25,000 students who are being enabled to be vanguards of their communities. Data were obtained through administration of semi-structured interview schedule students. Firstly, the interviews were conducted and the semi-structured schedule was administered, then Career Aspiration Scale (CAS) was given to the respondents for further data collection. A total sample size of 120 students (age group: 20 to 22) from both the sexes in equal proportion were collected. And the data for discussion with 10 case studies were taken and were content-analyzed. The data from the field was digitalized in a PC using MS Excel package, analysis was conducted using the same software and simple descriptive statistical method was used.

4.Result

Primary Analysis

Among the 120 respondents 70 were girls and the rest 50 were boys. For Science Stream among 40, 15 boys and 25 girls, Arts stream 40 (20 boys & 20 girls) and likewise Commerce- 23 boys and 13 girls. Numbers of years the respondents studying in the Institute, the 73% responded 5 years and 21% responded 3 years but the highest number of years was found 10 years responded 6%.

Mediation Analysis

In this study, Career Aspiration Scale was used and data collected each item under this scale was measured and was analyzed. The results show the respondents irrespectively Arts, Science and Commerce disciplines, more than 93% (students) scored 50 out 64; this indicates they have both achievement and educational aspiration at a higher level. Although some of the items such as: 1) 'I want to be among the very best in my field', 2) 'I plan to reach the highest level of education in my field', 3) 'I want my work to have a lasting impact on my field'; 95% (boys) respondents scored higher than the girls. However, the results also show the 91% (girls) respondents did positively good scores in items such as 4) 'I aspire to have my contribution at work recognized by my employer', 5) I will pursue additional training in my occupational areas of interest' and 7) 'Being outstanding at what I do at work is very important to me'.

Besides these findings from Career Aspiration Scale administered, analysis of qualitative data most objectively and systematically collected through one to one interaction indicates; 88%

respondents with higher educational aspiration were engaged in studies and studies related activities e.g. competitive exam preparation, soft skills development and development of computer skills. Probing with 5 main semi structured questions 87% respondents both boys and girls shows significant understanding about their future what they revealed through their *expressed career aspiration*, as manifested career aspiration not included in this study.

Figure-1: Perception about Career

Student' perception about career, both girls and boys and of different streams, point out mix responses. For 97% girls and 91% boys they opined that it is way of earning money for livelihood and it helps for self-dependence. Only 9% boys and 3% girls felt, it is sort of self – identity made through chosen profession. Stream wise: Arts 90% students expressed, through career they'll contribute to society and simultaneously fulfill their economic needs, Commerce 54% shared exclusively earning money for their personal accomplishment whereas the rest 46% opined the same as the Arts stream students did. And for Science, respondent students 93% stated, with good career they'll contribute to society, fulfill their economic needs and earned prestige and 7% responded, exclusively earning money for their personal accomplishment.

Table-1: Name of Career/Profession Students Aspire to be in.

Cluster	Group	Rank	Occupation	Girls	Boys	Total
High	1	1	Govt. Job (IAS/Grade-A, B,C)	13	7	17 %
		2	Medical-(Doctor/Nurse)	4	3	6 %
		3	Math-Science (Scientist)	0	1	1 %
	2	4	Technical (Engineer/Technician)	5	8	11 %
		5	Legal Work (Advocate/Judge)	4	2	5 %
		6	Management (Manager)	1	2	3 %
Medium	3	7	Education Work (Teacher/Lecturer)	29	16	38%
		8	Business & Trade (businessman)	0	1	1 %
		9	Computer (software/hardware/IT)	3	5	7 %

	4	10	Entertainment/Media (journalist/actor)	3	3	5 %
		11	Social & Political Services (developmental worker/ political leader)	1	2	3 %
		12	Art & Music Work (painter/musician)	3	0	3 %
Low	5	13	Skilled Crafts	4		3 %
		14	Personal Services (driver/caretaker)	0	0	0 %
		15	Clerical (peon)	0	0	0 %
	6	16	Sales Work (salesman)	0	0	0 %
		17	Agriculture	0	0	0 %
		18	Manual Work (coolie)	0	0	0 %
Total				70	50	

Among all the respondents 17% expressed their career aspiration in ‘Govt. Job (IAS/Grade-A, B, C)’ and the highest 38% shared they aspires to become teachers. But the in low cluster only 3% respondents that too girls prefer to be professional in ‘Skilled Crafts’ And the respondents were asked about ‘USP’ behind their such aspiration, all 120 respondents share about positive changes taken place due to the enabling environment and conducive academic ambience in the Institution; things like ‘ all facilities at free of cost, less disturbance, emotional support from teaching faculties, mindfulness, regularity in disposal of duties and responsibilities, more concentration in every sorts of academic activities and a feeling of joy and energy’ simply enliven them in the campus.

After 5 years where you will be’, the students’ response was found miscellaneous. There are respondents who opined that they would be settled and not remained unemployed. The highest number 41 girls will be in ‘Professional role (nurse, teacher, accountant, engineer, etc), and only 6 girls foresee they’d ‘Stay at home parent/homemaker’. Likewise girls, for boys, the trend is same.

Figure-2: Status After 5 years down the Lines

Being in your chosen career what will be your most important achievement/s and what will you do if not preferred career happens?’ The respondents’ top three achievements are i) Stable relationship, ii) Latest electronics gadgets iii) Owning home; very few respondents replied on ‘marriage and children’. Some of the important observations are like i) 2% respondents want to live in different part of the country, ii) 3% respondents irrespective of disciplines aim for higher education and training in university level, iii) 3% respondents wish to possess car and so on and so forth. Most significantly, there is none (no respondent) who consider ‘being rich enough to not have work’ and only 1% responded to have fame in life.

Figure-3: Most important achievement/s being in chosen career

5. Discussion of the result

The result from the this study brings together socio-economic factors, demographic factors and environmental factors and relate to psychological factors which influence on career decision making and achievement motivation for development of tribal students’ career aspiration. In this paragraph, results are not retold but the discussion deals with implication of finding along with supported case documentations:

Excerpt from Case-1: *“Being girl in our tribal community...you know what...! but I’ll do higher studies then think of marriage and settlement”*—Sumiata Ulka(B.A, Social Work)

Today’s knowledge economy surpasses everything and everyone irrespective of known and unknown obstacles aspires for growth and development, therefore it is no longer just literacy and education can meet the tribal developmental needs; increasingly its necessary for tribal students to have more aspiration especially career aspirations that can change traditional way of thinking and bring them to the mainstream.

Excerpt from Case-9: *“My parents were illiterate, they couldn’t read and write... but in my under graduation, I feel an extreme sort of passion to make some significant differences in our lifestyle”*—Binu Soren (B.Com, Accountancy)

In sociological perspective, career aspiration can be very good factor itself for social mobility; as it is known fact that tribal society severely lack mobility, that systematically put them in all sorts of vulnerabilities e.g. social, economic; and they encounter with multitude of challenges in day today life in this 21st century.

Excerpt from Case-7: *“We, tribals, although from marginal society but the education and exposures we are availing...make ourselves as change agent for societal uplift”* –Salma Munda (B.Sc, Compute Scienc)

The urge these days is to establish an initiative to ensure that each student irrespective of societal backgrounds, nurture higher aspiration so that they can develop required skills, engage with learning systems and make achievement--- a sort of embedded culture within the academic curriculum and infrastructures can pave or make positive change. And especially, in regard to ‘Skill India’ programme where development of human capital is concerned, the country’s youth aspiration counts a lot. For inclusive development the tribals too is the important stakeholders, hence tribal adolescent’s career aspiration—the factors playing vital role for its development are essentially to be reviewed.

6. Conclusion

This study on tribal undergraduate (UG) student’s dynamics of career aspiration precludes inferences about causality and or directionality. The study has properties of research; identical to psychosocial factors e.g. self-concept, self efficacy, motivation, and teaching-learning pedagogy are as the most important pillars for career aspiration of students. This may reckon the importance of enabling environment and innovative educational setting. But simultaneously it exhorts the importance of ‘access to facilities and exposures’ in higher education for maximization of students’ career aspiration. Participating students develop good amount of psychosocial potentials which are important for overall wellbeing too, positive self-

concept, knowing self (SWOT), employability and leadership skills etc. Therefore, it appears equally important student's engagement in their soft skills development and for every higher academic institution a career counseling as well as training & placement cell to help them flourishing with their chosen career.

From the findings, it indicates that students have higher career aspiration and they are incessantly trying their level best to come as successful in their career. However, it may sound more or less like an institutional case study and as the measures are not validated with higher level of statistical procedures, can be typical, exploring the dynamics of tribal students' career aspiration. Hence further research is needed to understand mediation between psychosocial factors and educational environment for development of career aspiration.

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